

SPECTRAL CALIBRATIONS OF HICO DATA USING ATMOSPHERIC BANDS AND RADIANCE ADJUSTMENT BASED ON HICO AND MODIS DATA COMPARISONS

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ABSTRACT

The Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICOTM) [1] instrument is now operating from a location on the Japanese Experiment Module-Exposed Facility (JEM-EF) on the International Space Station (ISS). HICOTM is a pushbroom sensor covering a spectral range between 0.35 and 1.08 micron with a spatial resolution of about 90 meter and a spectral sampling interval of 5.7 nanometer. The instrument is not equipped with radiometric and spectral calibration devices. Before shipping the HICOTM instrument to Japan to be launched on a Japanese HII-B rocket, spatial, spectral, and radiometric calibrations of the instrument were made in a calibration lab at the Naval Research Laboratory in Washington, DC. Based on the analysis of HICO data acquired from ISS, we have observed that the wavelengths of the HICO channels are slightly changed in comparison with those from laboratory calibrations. We have used a spectrum matching technique [2] for adjusting wavelengths. Several atmospheric water vapor and oxygen absorption bands in the HICO data measured under the normal operation mode with a spectral sampling interval of approximately 5.7 nm are used for spectrum matching. Four extra-terrestrial solar lines in the HICO data with a spectral spacing of 1.7 nm are also used for spectrum matching. The spectrum matching technique is described in this paper. Also based on analysis of ISS HICO data, we have found that the radiances of ISS HICO data calibrated with the laboratory-based coefficients are smaller than expected by approximately 25%. We have adjusted the calibration coefficients based on comparing HICO data and MODIS data acquired over several desert areas. The vicarious calibration procedure for HICO radiometric calibrations is also described in this paper.

Index Terms—Imaging Spectrometer, Coastal water, HICOTM, Hyperspectral imager, Spectrum matching, Wavelength calibrations, Spectral resolution calibration, Radiometric calibration, Vicarious calibration

1. INTRODUCTION

The Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICOTM) instrument is now collecting spectral imaging data from the International Space Station (ISS). It covers a solar spectral region between 0.35 and 1.08 micron with a spectral sampling spacing of 5.7 nm in 128 channels. The pixel size on the ground at the nadir looking direction is 90 m. The size of a typical HICO scene is roughly 42 km (cross track) by 192 km (along track). Figure 1 shows a sample HICO Level 1A (L1A) spectrum in digital counts, or digital numbers (DNs). In order to convert the L1A DN to the Level 1B (L1B) radiances, accurate radiometric and spectral calibrations must be made. The atmospheric water vapor bands centered near 0.725, 0.825, and 0.94 micron, the oxygen band near 0.765 micron, and a solar line near 0.43 micron, are obvious in this figure. These atmospheric and solar features allow the wavelength and spectral resolution calibrations from the HICO data itself.

Fig. 1. A sample HICO Level 1A spectrum in digital numbers (DNs). The atmospheric water vapor bands centered near 0.725, 0.825, and 0.94 micron, the oxygen band near 0.765 micron, and a solar line near 0.43 micron, are seen.

In this paper, a spectrum matching technique for HICO wavelength and spectral resolution calibrations is illustrated, and a vicarious calibration technique for

adjusting the gain factors used in HICO radiometric calibrations is described.

2. WAVELENGTH AND SPECTRAL RESOLUTION CALIBRATIONS

Spectral matching techniques [3] were developed in the 1970s for retrieving line positions and line widths from laboratory-measured “ultra” spectra (in which individual lines of atmospheric bands are resolved). Similar spectral matching techniques [2] have been used in the estimates of channel positions and spectral resolution from airborne imaging spectrometer data. A spectrum matching technique for HICO wavelength and spectral resolution calibrations is illustrated through examples below.

Figure 2 shows an example of a HICO spectrum covering the 0.765-micron oxygen band absorption region and a theoretically simulated atmospheric gas transmittance spectrum. When plotting the HICO spectrum, the wavelength file from pre-launch laboratory calibrations was used. From this figure, it is seen that the oxygen bands in the two spectra are relatively shifted, indicating a shift in wavelengths of HICO channels after the instrument was launched into space.

Fig. 2. An example of ISS HICO spectrum (solid line) covering the 0.765-micron oxygen band absorption region and a theoretically simulated atmospheric gas transmittance spectrum (dotted line).

In order to quantify the wavelength shift, we shift the wavelengths of the HICO channels from -3 nm to $+3$ nm (relative to the pre-launch laboratory-calibrated wavelengths) in steps of 0.02 nm. For each step, we make a nonlinear least squares matching between the measured spectrum and the simulated spectrum. The sum of the squared differences between the two spectra

is calculated. Figure 3 shows the best match between the measured spectrum (solid line) and the simulated spectrum (dotted line). The two spectra coincide almost exactly.

Fig. 3. An example of spectrum matching between the measured HICO spectrum (solid line) and the fitted spectrum (dotted line). The two spectra coincide almost exactly with each other in the best matching scenario.

Fig. 4. Sum of squared differences between the measured and fitted spectra as a function of wavelength shift. The minimum occurs for a wavelength shift of 1.7 nm.

Figure 4 is a plot of the sum of the squared differences as a function of wavelength shift. The minimum occurs at a wavelength shift of 1.7 nm. This is considered to be the best estimate of wavelength shift for the HICO instrument soon after launching into space in September of 2009. At present, the shift is about 0.9 nm.

Occasionally, the ISS HICO instrument collects data in the un-binned high spectral resolution mode. The wavelength interval between two adjacent channels is

approximately 1.9 nm and the spectral resolution is about 3.2 nm assuming a Gaussian response curve. Figure 5 shows a sample high spectral resolution HICO spectrum in digital numbers. Several solar lines below 0.8 micron are resolved better in this spectrum than those in the Fig. 1 spectrum. It should be pointed out that some of the high frequency features above 0.8 micron in the Fig. 5 spectrum are not real atmospheric or solar features. They are attributed to instrument artifacts.

Fig. 5. A sample HICO Level 1A spectrum in digital numbers (DNs) and measured in the un-binned high spectral resolution mode.

Fig. 6. A sample HICO Level 1A high resolution spectrum in digital numbers (DNs) and an extra-terrestrial solar irradiance spectrum.

In order to better reveal the solar lines, we show in Figure 6 the same high spectral resolution HICO spectrum (solid line) as that in Fig. 5, over a shorter wavelength interval, between 0.4 and 0.5 micron. Also shown in Fig. 6 is an extra-terrestrial MODTRAN solar irradiance curve (dotted line), which was smoothed to a spectral resolution of approximately 3 nm and vertically scaled to fit inside the plot. The solar lines

centered near 0.43 and 0.485 micron are well resolved in this spectrum. The two solar lines in the HICO spectrum and the MODTRAN spectrum are relatively shifted, similar to the spectral shift observed in the Fig. 2 spectra. Therefore, both the atmospheric oxygen band in Fig. 2 and the solar lines in Fig. 6 confirm a wavelength shift of HICO channels in the early stage of the ISS HICO data acquisition.

After the quantification of wavelength shift using the spectrum matching technique, as illustrated in Fig. 3 and 4, the spectral resolution of HICO data can be determined using the same technique. Figure 7 shows a curve of the sum of squared difference as a function of full width at half maximum (FWHM) by fitting an atmospheric water vapor absorption band centered near 0.725 micron in a HICO spectrum collected under the normal operational mode. The minimum occurs at a FWHM of 5.1 nm, which is considered to be the best estimate of the FWHM of the HICO instrument.

Fig. 7. Sum of squared differences between the measured and fitted spectra as a function of FWHM. The minimum occurs at a FWHM of 5.1 nm.

3. VICARIOUS RADIOMETRIC CALIBRATIONS

The radiances inferred from HICO data using the laboratory-based calibration coefficients are lower than expected. HICO does not carry any internal radiometric and spectral calibration devices, unlike the NASA Terra and Aqua MODIS instruments. In view of this situation, we have decided that one way to radiometrically calibrate the HICO data is to transfer the MODIS radiometric calibrations to the HICO radiometric calibrations through inter-satellite data comparisons. The MOBY site [4] off the coast of Lanai, Hawaii, is the site used by the NASA ocean color community for the calibration of SeaWiFS and Terra and Aqua MODIS instruments. This site is also placed on the HICO target list for repeated data collections. Through analysis of a

number of data sets measured over the MOBY site, we have concluded that this site is not really quite suited for inter-satellite data comparisons. One fact is that this site is often covered by thin cirrus clouds. Another fact is that the radiances for the two most important narrow atmospheric correction channels centered near 0.75 and 0.865 micron over clear waters are very low.

Fig. 8. An example of inter-satellite data comparison between HICO and MODIS.

Fig. 9. Examples of spectrally and radiometrically calibrated HICO radiance spectra measured over clear deep ocean waters, shallow coastal waters, green vegetation, and clouds.

Although HICO is, among other things, an ocean color instrument, it does not saturate over high reflecting desert areas, unlike the Terra and Aqua MODIS ocean color channels that saturate over land surfaces and over coastal waters. We have decided to use desert calibration sites previously used by the Landsat Science Team and the NASA EO-1 Science Team for inter-satellite comparisons. Pairs of HICO data and MODIS data have been acquired over several desert calibration sites. Figure 8 shows an example of inter-satellite data comparison between HICO and MODIS land channels. Fig. 8a is a HICO RGB image

acquired over an area in the Middle East. Fig. 8b is an Aqua MODIS image acquired the same day. We manually selected small spatially uniform common areas in both images, and averaged the HICO data and MODIS data, respectively. Fig. 8c shows the HICO and MODIS radiances as a function of wavelength. The HICO radiances are, on average, lower than the corresponding MODIS radiances by approximately 25%. Based on such inter-satellite data comparisons and on the consideration of cloud reflectance properties (water cloud reflectances in the 0.35 – 1.08 micron spectral region are almost constant) we have derived an empirical scaling curve, and multiplied the curve to the laboratory-based radiometric calibration curve. The resulting curve is used for radiometric calibrations of HICO data. Figure 9 shows examples of radiometrically calibrated HICO radiance spectra over clear waters, shallow waters with bottom reflection, green vegetation, and clouds. From the HICO L1B data, quite reasonable Level 2 surface reflectance data products have been retrieved.

4. SUMMARY

A spectrum matching technique has been developed for wavelength and spectral resolution calibrations of HICO data using atmospheric bands and solar lines contained in the data. Vicarious techniques based on inter-comparison between HICO data and MODIS data and based on water cloud reflectance properties have also been developed for radiometric calibrations of HICO data.

5. REFERENCES

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